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Cybercrime And The Perceived Challenges Of Detection And Prosecution

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ABSTRACT

The study interrogated cybercrime and the perceived challenges of detecting and prosecuting same. Cybercrime is a speedy growing area of crime and represents one of the most serious challenges to nations and the international community at large. Attraction for cybercrime stems from the speed, convenience and anonymity with which a range of crimes can be committed using computers and the Internet. Cybercrime constitutes constant international threat affecting and acting beyond national borders. The study employed majorly the doctrinal research method using descriptive and analytical approaches to capture a detailed outlook of the challenge was investigated. The study found that increased risks and threats to the cyberspace mean that more international cybercriminals are exploiting the weak online environment or non-existent cyberspace law enforcement strategies to commit cybercrimes. This research found as well that some challenges surrounding the prosecution of cybercrimes also hold true for detection of cybercrimes such as anonymity and jurisdiction, amongst others. The paper argued that insofar as identified challenges confronting the investigation and prosecution of cybercrime are not effectively dealt with, threats to cyberspace will continue to increase. Accordingly, the study recommended amongst others that online users can help stem the tide of cyber criminality and consequently reduce challenges to investigators and prosecutors by first learning how to protect themselves in the following ways: (a) guarding their identities and information when they go online, (b) ensuring that public computers are not used for transactions that require online payment, (c) not responding to phony emails and offers that ask for password and or personal information; and (d) ensuring that their computers are protected with strong, updated security software.

Keywords: Cybercrime, cyber security, detection, prevention, prosecution, national security

INTRODUCTION

Cybercrime is a fast-rising area of crime and represents one of the most serious challenges to the international community at large. Attraction for cybercrime stems from the speed, convenience and anonymity with which a range of crimes can be committed using computers and the Internet. As observed by Nuredini,¹ cybercrime constitutes constant international threat affecting and acting beyond national borders. Rather than abate, cyber-attacks and disruptions continue to increase due to continued digitalization of not only existing business models but also of criminal groups aspiration to disrupt communication flows. In that, the international community concedes that: (a) the digitalization and interconnectivity, particularly critical infrastructure plays a critical role in increasing the risks of both fortuitous and deliberate cyber interferences; and (b) the threat to cyberspace is real.² The reality of threat to the cyberspace is further portrayed in studies that reveal a dramatic increase in recent years, with more than 590 million people affected-one way or another globally as at 2015³ in the same way that cybercrime affects development negatively.

Increased risks and threats to the cyberspace mean that more international cybercriminals are exploiting the weak online environment or non-existent cyberspace law enforcement strategy, to commit crimes. The importance of the cyberspace and the need to secure same against forms of criminality arises out of the fact that cyberspace is a fundamental element of critical national and

¹ Ahmet Nuredini, 'Challenges in Combating the Cyber Crime' (2014) *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* Vol. 5 No 19

² See United Nations Office for Disarmament (UNODA), *Developments in the Field of Information Technology and Telecommunications in the Context of International Security* (2016) Report of the Secretary-General, available at, <http://www.un.org>, accessed 20 July 2016.

³ See Norton Cyber Security Insights Report 2016, available at, <http://www.us.norton.com>, accessed 30 July 2022.

international infrastructure,⁴ with attendant implications for national security.⁵ The purpose of this work is to examine the nature of cybercrime in relation to its variance with traditional crimes in terms of the method of commission.

The paper argues that insofar as identified challenges confronting the investigation and prosecution of cybercrime are not effectively dealt with, threats to cyberspace will continue to increase. For purposes of seamlessness, issues under review are thematically discussed in four segments. While the first segment is a general introduction to the issue of cybercrime, the second segment examines the nature of cybercrimes. The third segment, which is the kernel of this work, assesses the challenges surrounding the detection and prosecution of cybercrimes. The last segment principally evaluates international and national legal framework as well as strategies/measures adopted with special focus on eliminating or reducing incidences of cybercrimes. Conclusion is consequential upon analysis of issues.

Nature of Cybercrime

Conduct that amounts to cybercrime is [usually] specifically criminalized and is not essentially different from conduct already criminalized in national and international criminal jurisdictions. In Nigeria for example, certain conducts are established as criminal and constitutes cybercrimes under previously existing pockets of provisions prohibiting computer related crimes -Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) Act, 2004 and Independent Corrupt Practices and other Related Offences (ICPC) Act 2000,⁶ as well as the new Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc.) Act, 2015 with the 2025 amendment Act of same (CPPA). Such conduct includes tampering with critical infrastructure,⁷ forgery and fraud,⁸ Cyber terrorism,⁹ child pornography,¹⁰ theft of electronic devices, cyber stalking, cybersquatting, racist and xenophobic conducts, manipulation of ATM/POS terminals, spreading virus to computers, phishing and spamming, amongst others.¹¹ This means that cybercrimes are not different from traditional crimes and principally fits into the categorization of *offences against the person, offences against property, offences against the state*, amongst others. The difference here is that, rather than commit these crimes in the same conventional manner, criminals exploit electronic devices in committing these traditional crimes.¹²

This phenomenon no doubt calls for concerted international action. Thus, at the 13th United Nations Congress on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice, the following conclusions were drawn in relation to cybercrime - (a) cybercrime is an “emerging form of transnational crime, and one of the fastest growing criminal activities;”¹³ and (b) increasing reliance on the internet- by an estimated two billion people globally, for information and communication, also attracts criminals because they can remain unidentified and be able to access personal and official information that have been stored online. For the UN, the international community must, as a matter of urgency find innovative tools to fight these “emerging threats”-cybercrime, terrorism recruitment, Botnets,¹⁴ online spies and terrorists recruiting foreign fighters etc.¹⁵

Highlighting the imperatives to urgently “erect legal barriers” for cybercrimes, the UN observed that new global treaties that can potentially end “impunity, prosecute perpetrators and stop cybercrime and illicit financing in their tracks”¹⁶ must be adopted and adequately implemented. This is important in view of the fact that criminals may “technologically” outsmart law enforcement and pose serious threat to global, regional and national stability. Although there are several forms of cybercrime, malware,¹⁷ identity-related offences¹⁸ and hacking¹⁹ are the most common. Other forms of crimes

⁴ Ibid

⁵ Ibid

⁶ For example, sections 15 (a) and 42 (2) (a) ICPC Act empowers the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission to prosecute persons who destroy equipment used in committing corruption, including computer system, and also to inspect instruments suspected to be objects of corruption, including computers.

⁷ Section 10 of CPPA.

⁸ See sections 13 and 14 (1) of CPPA.

⁹ Section 18 CPPA.

¹⁰ Section 23 (1).

¹¹ See sections 24-36 of CPPA

¹² B.J. Koops, 'The Internet and its Opportunities for Crime,' in Herzog-Evans (ed), *Transnational Criminology Manual* (2010) Nijmegen, Netherlands, WLP, pp. 735-754; See also M. Yar, *The Novelty of Cybercrime: An Assessment in Light of Routine Activity Theory*(2005), *European Journal of Criminology* 2 (4) 407-427.

¹³ See 13th United Nations congress on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice, Doha, 12-19 April 2015; available at <http://www.un.org/en/events/crimecongress2015/conference-programme>, accessed 20 July 2022.

¹⁴ A botnet is an interconnected network of computers infected with malware without the user's knowledge and controlled by cybercriminals. They're typically used to send spam emails, transmit viruses and engage in other acts of cybercrime. Sometimes known as a zombie army, botnets are often considered one of the biggest online threats today. See *What is Botnet?*, available at, <http://www.usa.kaspersky.com>; accessed 12 august 2022

¹⁵ See Meetings and Press Releases at, <http://www.un.org>; accessed 12 August 2022

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ This occurs by phishing (deceiving Internet users into giving their personal information).

¹⁸ Unintentionally-installed software that collects personal information.

commonly committed on the Internet are those related to copyright and intellectual property rights, child pornography, terrorism and abuse of materials. Having said that, it becomes important to express, in definite terms, what constitutes cybercrimes.

The meaning of cybercrime is subjective and typically depends on the purpose of its use. A limited number of actions against the confidentiality, integrity and availability of computer data or systems represent the core of cybercrime. Beyond this, however, computer-related acts for personal or financial gain or harm, including forms of identity-related crime, and computer content-related acts fall within a wider meaning of the term 'cybercrime' even though these do not lend themselves easily to efforts to arrive at legal definitions of the cumulative term.²⁰ But certain definitions are required for the core of cybercrime acts. In that wider sense therefore, cybercrime is defined as a crime in which a computer is either the object of the crime (e.g. phishing,²¹ hacking²² and spamming,²³) or is used as a tool to commit an offense (e.g. cyber terrorism, child pornography, fraud or hate crimes). To illustrate further, cybercriminals may access personal information, organizations and business trade secrets, stored online through a computer; and they may also use the Internet for abusive or malevolent reasons.²⁴ These actions transcend national boundaries effectively according cybercrime a transnational character, in which perpetrators could commit a crime, e.g. cyber fraud in a country other than their place of domicile.

A cursory look at the definitions and character of cybercrime reveals active use of a computer system, raising the imperatives for examining the meaning of computer. At international level, computer system is defined in article 1 (a) of the Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention) as "any device or a group of interconnected or related devices, one or more of which, pursuant to a program, performs automatic processing of data."²⁵ In the same vein, section 58 of the Nigerian CPPA, 2015 defines a computer system as "...an electronic, magnetic, optical, electrochemical or other high speed data processing device performing logical, arithmetic, or storage functions and includes any data storage facility. All communication devices that can directly interface with a computer through communication protocols shall form part of this definition. This definition excludes the following; portable hand-held calculator typewriters and typesetters or other similar devices.

This wide definition of computer system goes beyond a traditional computer to cover other devices such as mobile phones, tablets and similar devices that possess the ability to interface with a computer and can process data. A peculiar nature of cybercrime relates to the ease with which it can be committed owing to growth in technology that allows everyone and anyone- skillful in technology or not, to be a threat.²⁶ For instance, software programmes that allow people to locate open ports or override password protection can be bought effortlessly online, which principally makes it easy for people who do not possess technological skills to breach cyber security.²⁷ To that extent, they pose serious threat to cyberspace and breach cyber security. In 2011 for example, Norton²⁸ undertook a study in which the organization revealed a dramatic increase in cyber threat in 2010 with 431 million

¹⁹ Illegally accessing someone's computer remotely). Criminals tend to use these methods to steal credit card information and money

²⁰ Arthur Appazov, *Legal Aspects of Cybersecurity* (2014), University of Copenhagen; available at, [http://justitsministeriet.dk/sites/default/files/media/Arbejdsomraader/Forskning/Forskningspuljen/Legal Aspects of Cybersecurity.pdf](http://justitsministeriet.dk/sites/default/files/media/Arbejdsomraader/Forskning/Forskningspuljen/Legal%20Aspects%20of%20Cybersecurity.pdf), accessed 25 July 2022.

²¹ Phishing is a fraudulent attempt, usually made through email, to steal personal information. Such emails would usually attempt to redirect the target to another page where the victim would divulge personal information such as credit card details, passwords etc. Such emails usually appear as coming from reputable organizations. See Anti-Phishing Working Group (APWG) at <http://www.antiphishing.org>, accessed 20 July 2022.

²² Hacking is the act of immersing oneself in computer systems details to optimize their capabilities. See Webster's New World Hacker Dictionary available at, <http://computer.yourdictionary.com>, accessed 21 July 2022.

²³ Spamming means swamping the Internet with many copies of the same message, in an attempt to force the message on people who would not otherwise choose to receive it. Most spam is commercial advertising, often for dubious products, get-rich-quick schemes, or quasi-legal services. For more information on spamming, see Internet Society, *A Short Guide to Spam*, available at, <http://www.internetsociety.org/spam/short-guide-spam>, accessed 22 July 2022.

²⁴ Interpol, *Cybercrime*, available at, <http://www.interpol.int>, accessed 27 august 2022

²⁵ Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention) ETS 185 -23.XI.2001; The Council of Europe with the participation of Canada, Japan, South Africa and the USA elaborated the Convention. It opened for signature in Budapest in November 2001 and has been in force since July 2004.

²⁶ Cybersecurity is a complex intercontinental matter that requires international collaboration to ensure and sustain security on the cyberspace. See generally Microsoft, *The Cybersecurity Risk Paradox: Impact of Social, Economic, and Technological Factors on Rates of Malware* (2014) Microsoft Security Intelligence Report, Special Edition, available at <http://download.microsoft.com/download/E/1/8/E18A8FBB-7BA6-48BD-97D2-9CD32A71B434/Cybersecurity-Risk-Paradox.pdf>; accessed 25 July 2022.

²⁷ UNODC, *Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime* (2013: New York, United Nations), pp. 44-50.

²⁸ See Norton Cyber security Insights Report 2016.

adults being attacked globally-14 adults victims every second, one million cybercrime victims every day, and a further increase of the number of victims to over 590 million people as of 2015 (already noted above).²⁹

Generally, cybercrime has assumed the nature of profitable business, raking in trillion dollars annually in identity theft, online fraud, and lost intellectual property;³⁰ and every nation-governments, institutions, businesses and organizations as well as individuals are affected. There is no doubt that the proliferation of information and communication technologies proffer great opportunity in many respects, it also creates room for insecurity and cyber criminality. This effectively calls for security measures to safeguard the cyberspace.

The nature of cybercrime as a transnational criminal activity means that the activity remains a challenge, thanks to factors that includes, improper/inadequate regulation, insufficient capacity or inability to identify cybercriminals, especially in developing countries as well as the ability of criminals to hide behind lacunae in the law and weak security measures of countries with feeble regulations to perpetrate cybercrime amongst others. For these and several other reasons, the international community is calling for an urgent and robust international response to cybercrime, specifically stating that, "global effort is needed to provide better protection and firmer regulations."³¹

Challenges in Detecting and Prosecuting Cybercrime: Overview

It is incontrovertible that computers and information communication technology (ICT) has orchestrated and enhanced criminal activities that transcend borders, with some assuming the nature of transnational organized criminality. Consequently, countries are required to establish and or enhance cyber security measures capable of detecting and aiding investigation and prosecution of cybercrimes. Such measures-legal, administrative and policy must also be able to effectively tackle the threat of cybercrimes. As cybercrimes can be transnational in nature, countries need to seriously consider inter-country as well as inter-agency cooperation in the area of cyber security. The need to cooperate arises out of the (a) existence of the vexed issue of legal pluralism, (b) need to eliminate the contours of criminal law provisions of countries through harmonization, (c) need to deal with complex jurisdictional issues; and (d) exigencies of developing new cooperation procedures that challenge cybercrime in all ramifications. Addressing these issues could, to a large extent potentially lead to effective fight against cyber threats.

While countries-individually and collectively have expressed the will and desire to detect, investigate and prosecute cybercrimes, they face serious difficulties especially cross-border process of identifying, investigating and securing electronic evidence of the specific offence through prosecution and eventual conviction and punishment of the perpetrator (s) in any "complaint jurisdiction",³² within the framework of human rights. Effective detection, investigation and prosecution of cybercrime hinge upon law enforcement being armed with legal tools, particularly well-defined cyber offences for prosecuting and procedural rules governing evidence gathering and investigation. The nature of cybercrime as transnational criminality means that the legal regime of countries must be constructed in a way that ensures that their penal and procedural law is adequate to meet the challenges it pose.

Challenges in Prosecution Jurisdictional issues

The issue of jurisdiction is one that has been dealt with extensively by writers³³ due principally to its critical place in the prosecution of cybercrime. The critical place of jurisdiction in prosecution of cybercrime is tied to its nature as crime that transcends criminal justice systems.³⁴ The critical place of jurisdiction in any criminal prosecution, including cybercrime was aptly captured in the Nigerian case of *Utih & Ors v Onoyivwe & Ors*³⁵ where the Supreme Court (SC) described jurisdiction as the "...blood that gives life to the survival of an action in a court of law" without which "the action will be like an animal that has been drained of its blood..." Also, in *UBA Plc. & Ors v Ademola*,³⁶ the court established that jurisdiction "is the livewire of a court as no court can entertain a matter where it lacks jurisdiction."³⁷

²⁹ Toby Mendel, Andrew Puddephatt, Global Survey on Internet Privacy and Freedom of Expression (2012) UNESCO Series on Internet Freedom, pp.55-67.

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ See generally, P. M. Tehrani, NA Manap, H Taji, Cyber terrorism challenges: The need for global response to a multi-jurisdictional crime (2013) Computer Law and Security Review, vol. 29 (3) 207-215.

³² Alain Megias, How Cyber Jurisdiction Affects Cybercrime Prosecution; available at, <http://www.i-policy.org/2011/02/how-cyber-jurisdiction-affects-cybercrime-prosecution.html>; accessed 22 July 2022

³³ See Susan W. Brenner, 'Is There Such a Thing as Virtual Crime?'(2001) California Criminal Law Review, available at, <http://boalt.org/CCLR/>, accessed 30 July 2022. See also, J, Kremer, B.Müller, Cyberspace and International Relations: Theory, Prospects and Challenges (2014) Springer, Heidelberg, 19

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ (1991) LPELR-3436 (SC); (1991) 1SCNJ 25; (1991) 1 S.C (Pt. 1) 61.

³⁶ (2008) LPELR-5066(CA).

³⁷ Ibid

Jurisdiction defines boundaries within which an agency or court has power to hear and determine civil and criminal matters; and extends to the scope of a court's procedural and substantive power to hear and determine criminal cases. The nature of a court's jurisdiction over procedural and substantive issues was examined by the Court of Appeal (CA) in *Akaniyene & Ors v Etta*³⁸ where Ndukwe-Anyanwu JCA examined the character of substantive and procedural jurisdiction and concluded that a litigant can waive jurisdiction relating to procedural law but cannot do so with substantive law, noting that "litigant may submit to the procedural jurisdiction of the court,"³⁹ and relying on *Dairo v UBA*⁴⁰ the court states in *UBA Plc. supra*, that jurisdiction is decisive and can be raised at any time even on appeal. Importantly, the authority of a court to hear and determine hinges upon a number of factors, such as the type of case, grade of the offence, punishment to be meted out, type of pecuniary award and the level of government.⁴¹

Ordinarily, jurisdiction means territory, specifically the limits of a country's territorial boundaries.⁴² But the Black's Law Dictionary defines it legally as "a court's power to decide a case or issue."⁴³ The problem with invoking the ordinary meaning of jurisdiction for purposes of prosecuting cybercrimes is tricky mainly because determining where a cybercrime was "committed" is difficult since the offender and the victim may be in different nations; and further, the offender may exploit computer systems in more than one country in the course of committing the offence.⁴⁴ A recommended approach therefore would be to expand the definition of jurisdiction to prosecute in a manner that permits the country to prosecute any cybercrime that is committed partly or wholly within the territory of the prosecuting country.⁴⁵

The expanded definition should normally give the country jurisdiction to prosecute a cybercriminal in the following settings: (a) when both the victim(s) and the criminal were located in the country at the time of committing the crime and the offender exploited computer technology situated in that country; (b) when either the victim or the criminal was located in that country during the commission of the cybercrime; and/or (c) when any part of the crime was committed, planned or facilitated in that country. In the same vein, countries can enact their own criminal provisions that govern their citizens when the citizens are abroad. Doing this simply means that a citizen of the particular country can be prosecuted for cybercrime committed although the citizen actually committed the crime in another country even if the conduct did not have harmful effects on the prosecuting country-its people and or property according to Hunton.⁴⁶

In the particular context of challenges posed by jurisdictional issues, usually, even where cybercriminals are detected, arresting and taking them into custody and prosecuting them could be difficult-except where some form of cooperation exists between the arresting authority and the country where the criminal is found (assuming they are different). For example, cooperation between the Interpol and the Nigerian Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) led to the arrest of a 40-year-old Nigerian national, known as 'Mike', believed to be behind scams totaling more than USD 60 million involving hundreds of victims worldwide in Port Harcourt. The suspect was implicated in Internet scamming that affected businesses in Australia, Canada, India, Malaysia, Romania, South Africa, Thailand and the US.⁴⁷ In this particular instance, the suspect can be prosecuted in Nigeria under the Cybercrime (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc.) Act, (CPPA) 2015, section 50⁴⁸ of which gives wide jurisdiction to a Federal High Court sitting in any part of Nigeria to try cybercrimes. If a foreign country where the cybercriminal is resident is unwilling or lacks technical competence to assist investigators, then taking into custody and prosecuting may be challenging.

³⁸ (2012) LPELR-9792 (CA).

³⁹ Ibid

⁴⁰ (2007) All F. W. L. R para 392 p.1846 al pages 1872-1873 HB

⁴¹ Legal provisions that establish such courts usually provide for jurisdiction of courts with regards to the enumerated issues. See for example Chapter VII: The Judicature, of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN), 1999, as amended.

⁴² See Auriel Sari, 'Jurisdiction and International Responsibility in Peace Support Operations: The Behrami and Saramati Cases' (2008) Human Rights Review, Vol. 8, Issue 1, pp.151-170.

⁴³ See the Black's Law Dictionary 9th edition, p.927.

⁴⁴ Bernadette H. Schell, Miguel Vargas Martin, Patrick C.K. Hung, Luis Rueda, 'Cyber child pornography: A review paper of the social and legal issues and remedies-and a proposed technological solution'(2007) Aggression and Violent Behavior, Vol. 12, Issue 1, pp. 45-63.

⁴⁵ Ibid

⁴⁶ P. Hunton, The states of cybercrime investigations: Bridging the gap between technology examination and law enforcement investigation (2011) Computer Law and Security Review, vol. 27 (1), pp.61-67

⁴⁷ See Interpol, Ringleader of global network behind thousands of online scams arrested in Nigeria, available at <http://www.interpol.int>, accessed 2 August 2022.

⁴⁸ Section 50 provides: (1) The Federal High Court located in any part of Nigeria regardless of the location where the offence is committed shall have jurisdiction to try offences under this Act, if committed- (a)in Nigeria; or (b) in a ship or aircraft registered in Nigeria; or (c) by a citizen or resident in Nigeria if the person's conduct would also constitute an offence under a law of the country where the offence was committed; or (d) outside Nigeria, where - (i) the victim of the offence is a citizen or resident of Nigeria; or (ii) the alleged offender is in Nigeria and not extradited to any other country for prosecution.

The extraterritoriality of cybercrime would usually provoke the issues of legal pluralism and dual criminality both of which raise the question whether conduct amounting to cybercrime is also criminalized in countries affected by the conduct. It is to address this variance that the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crimes (UNCTOC)⁴⁹ enjoin states parties to harmonize their criminal laws, to promote seamless cooperation in the area of extradition and mutual legal assistance in relation to offences under the Convention.

To steer countries on this part of cooperation and harmonization of legal provisions, the Interpol established a plan for international cooperation against crime, including cybercrime that most countries have joined,⁵⁰ while the UN continues to call on states to examine their procedural laws to see whether they are amenable to other systems to enable them assume jurisdiction over cybercrimes.⁵¹ This is important because as a general rule, law enforcement agencies are only empowered to enforce law within their jurisdictions and not otherwise; hence enforcing transnational crimes become extremely difficult.⁵² Normally, states are not under obligation to hand over a suspect to a requesting state or entity except where specific extradition treaty has been agreed. Even where such agreements exist, the process of securing extradition is usually lengthy, complex and expensive.⁵³ This situation could potentially force countries to adopt extra-judicial means in securing the presence of a suspect.

Again, under general criminal law principles, crime (s) committed within the borders of a country should be tried under the national law of that country except for persons covered by immunity.⁵⁴ But this obstacle is gradually being overcome by virtue of international and national law provisions that tend to tackle the issue of jurisdiction. For example, section 50 of CPPA (already referred to above) tackled the issue of jurisdiction at national level while article 22 of the Budapest Convention, notes that jurisdiction should exist when cybercrime is committed in the territory of a state, on board a ship flying the flag of that party; or on board an air craft registered under the laws of that party; or by one of its nationals. The Convention also require state parties to establish jurisdiction over its nationals and to prosecute them where as a matter of national law, such persons may not be extradited to a requesting state where the crime was committed. This would address the issue of "dual criminality",⁵⁵ which often pose serious challenges in cybercrime investigation and prosecution.

Anonymity

Anonymity remains one of the biggest challenges both in detecting and in prosecuting cybercrimes, as it makes it difficult for law enforcement operatives "to profile and locate criminals" according to the UN,⁵⁶ which means that this could undermine prosecution efforts since the identity of a suspect and the place where the offence is committed must first be established before investigation, arrest and prosecution for the offence can begin. This is also significant for ascertaining the jurisdiction of court according to Eugene Kaspersky.⁵⁷ For him, the existence of several ways of hiding one's identity, especially in relation to online criminality constitutes a serious obstacle in detecting cybercrime, more so because of the proliferation of services that are willing to disguise a client's by "routing traffic through several servers," usually upon payment of a stipulated fee; thereby making it extremely difficult to track down persons involved in online criminality. This anonymity accounts for why cybercrime is attractive to organized criminal gangs according to the United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute (UNICRI) which notes that "more than three quarters of

⁴⁹ The United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, adopted by General Assembly resolution 55/25 of 15 November 2000, is the main international instrument in the fight against transnational organized crime. It opened for signature by Member States at a High-level Political Conference convened for that purpose in Palermo, Italy, on 12-15 December 2000 and entered into force on 29 September 2003. The Convention is further supplemented by three Protocols, which target specific areas and manifestations of organized crime: the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children; the Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air; and the Protocol against the Illicit Manufacturing of and Trafficking in Firearms, their Parts and Components and Ammunition. Countries must become parties to the Convention itself before they can become parties to any of the Protocols

⁵⁰ Ibid

⁵¹ See UNODC, *Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime* (2013: New York, United Nations), pp. 50-60. See also, A. Guichard, *Between Hype and Understatement: Reassessing Cyber Risks as a Security Strategy* (2011); available at, <http://scholarcommons.usf.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=11107&context=jss>, accessed 25 August 2022

⁵² See Armando Cottim, 'Cybercrime, Cyber terrorism and Jurisdiction: An Analysis of Article 22 of COE Convention on Cybercrime' (2010) *European Journal of Legal Studies* Vol. 3, No. 2, 1

⁵³ See European Commission, *Mutual legal assistance and extradition*, available at, <http://www.ec.europa.eu>; accessed 28 July 2022

⁵⁴ See Article 31 of the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relation 196

⁵⁵ L. Moraski, *Cybercrime Knows No Borders* (2011) *Infosecurity*, vol.8(2):20-23.

⁵⁶ R. Bryant (ed), *Policing Digital Crime* (2016) Routledge, New York USA, pp.111-123

⁵⁷ Eugene Kaspersky, *The Cybercrime Arms Race* (2008), White Paper, pp.5-6

cybercrime acts today are linked to organized criminal activity due to anonymity that the Internet offers.”⁵⁸

The Interpol,⁵⁹ in alluding to sharp increase in cyber criminality, noted that "the speed, convenience and anonymity of the Internet" is what inspires criminals to “commit a diverse range of criminal activities that know no borders, either physical or virtual, cause serious harm and pose very real threats to victims worldwide”⁶⁰ Similarly, at the 13th United Nations Congress on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice at Doha, the United Nations Information Service (UNIS),⁶¹ observed that "with some two billion users worldwide, cyberspace is the ideal place for criminals because they can remain anonymous and gain access to all forms of personal information we knowingly, or unwittingly, store online".⁶² The dilemma is further aggravated by human rights concerns-relating to right to privacy, which often results in criticism, whenever imperatives for tracking online identity arises. On the flip side, unveiling and or ending anonymity is likely to have severe consequences, especially in states where "governments punishes dissenters", and this has been argued to contribute to the challenge that anonymity pose. Thus, assuming that the difficult problem of identifying cyber users-and by extension cybercriminals can be surmounted, the likelihood that lawmakers in some countries would be hesitant in authorizing this by legislation remains. Fundamentally, this speaks to the issue of rights, freedoms and privileges-including anonymity existing in democratic societies that cybercriminals take undue advantage of to commit a series of crimes that benefits them.

Nature of the Evidence

Evidence generally connotes facts (including testimony, documents and tangible objects) that tends to prove or disprove the existence of an alleged fact".⁶³ It goes without saying that evidence is significant particularly for prosecution of cybercrime. The nature of evidence that would establish the offence of cybercrime is also crucial, in this case, digital evidence.⁶⁴ Generally, digital evidence is fragile and can be easily changed or lost,⁶⁵ more so because it is mainly a "collection of ones and zeros represented by magnetization, light pulses, radio signals or other means" ⁶⁶ In every criminal case that require criminal facts to be proved “beyond every reasonable doubt”,⁶⁷evidence retrieved or gathered in relation to the commission of the offence must be protected and a clear chain of custody maintained. This is extremely difficult in the case of cybercrime due to the fragility of digital evidence referred to above, especially with the possibility of investigator contaminating evidence during the process of examination. There is also a possibility that high-tech cybercriminals could configure their computers in a way that ensures that evidence is automatically destroyed once any other person accesses the computer.⁶⁸ One very difficult area where gathering and maintaining the integrity of digital evidence remains a challenge is in the area of child pornography. For example, how do you prove knowledge where someone downloads illegal materials, especially in era of computer and or account hackings? Presently, situations involving the hacking into systems and stored data without the owner's knowledge and or authorization by criminals are common.⁶⁹ Again cybercriminals have been said to erase logs that might incriminate them for purposes of destroying evidence to establish the commission of a crime; hence establishing a cybercriminal conduct-especially in developing countries that lack resources and expertise to track such crimes, remains challenging,⁷⁰ especially in jurisdictions that first of all, do not recognize electronic evidence.

⁵⁸ See United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute (UNICRI), Cybercrime and Organized Crime, available at, <http://www.unicri.it>, accessed 22 august 2022.

⁵⁹ Interpol, Cybercrime, available at <http://www.interpol.int>, accessed 18 July 2022

⁶⁰ Ibid

⁶¹ See UNIS, Cybercrime, available at, <http://www.unis.unvienna.org>; accessed 18 July 2022

⁶² Ibid

⁶³ See the Black’s Law Dictionary, 9th Edition, at p.635

⁶⁴ Digital evidence is any information or data of value to an investigation that is stored on, received by, or transmitted by an electronic device. Text messages, emails, pictures and videos, and Internet searches are some of the most common types of digital evidence. More information on this can be obtained at, <http://www.iacpcybercenter.org/officers/digital-evidence/>; accessed 25 June 2022.

⁶⁵ UNODC, Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime (2013), Report prepared for the Open-Ended Intergovernmental Expert Group on Cybercrime, New York: United Nations; available at http://www.unodc.org/documents/organizedcrime/UNODC_CCPCJ_EG.4_2013/CYBER_STU_DY_210213.pdf; accessed 22 July 2022

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ See section 135 (1) of the Evidence Act, 2011. See also the case of Ahmed v the State (1999) NWLR (Pt. 612) 673

⁶⁸ B. W. Boehm, Software Engineering Economics (1984); available at, https://extras.springer.com/2002/978-3-642-59413-7/4/ron/pdf/Boehm_hist.pdf, accessed 24 August 2022.

⁶⁹ Reference the recent hacking of the National Democratic Committee (NDC) emails in the United States of America by Wikileaks; available at, <http://www.cnn.com>, accessed 28 July 2022

⁷⁰ UNODC, Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime (2013: New York, United Nations), pp. 72-77.

The Evidence Act 2011 has to a large extent clarified Nigerian position on electronically generated evidence; and introduced mandatory technicalities, which must be adverted to by counsel or risk rejection of evidence as far as generating electronic evidence is concerned. However, facilities and expertise to generate such evidence remains a problem.

Usually, evidence required in cybercrime is electronic in nature-gathered forensically from the Internet and computer hard disk or software belonging to the accused person. It means the right equipment and high level of expertise must be available for digital evidence to be generated; and of course comes the issue of admissibility of such evidence. As noted above, the 2011 Evidence Act, which also stipulates conditions upon which such evidence can be admitted, governs admissibility of electronic evidence.⁷¹

However, there have always been misgivings with regards to evidence generated electronically from Internet sources. For example, some courts in the United States of America have been averse to such evidence for its unreliability. In the case of *St. Clair v Johnny's Oyster and Shrimp*,⁷² the court vilified the "so called web," and concluded that evidence procured off the internet is adequate for almost nothing, amounts to hearsay, prejudicial, irrelevant and incapable of authentication for the following reasons; (a) it provides no way of "verifying the authenticity of the alleged contentions," (b) it is porous-anyone can put anything in the internet, (c) lack of monitoring of websites for accuracy; and (d) nothing contained therein is under an oath or even subject to independent verification absent underlying documentation. The court expressed similar opinion in the case of *United State v. Johnson*.⁷³

In Nigeria, the courts continue to face challenges in respect of admissibility of electronically generated evidence as development in the law of evidence relating to electronic evidence remains slow. Before the amendment of the 1945 Evidence Act in 2011, electronically generated evidence was inadmissible. That is not to say that the Nigerian courts do not recognize developments in ICT crime and the need to admit electronically generated evidence; and so the courts have in, some cases, been proactive in dealing with electronic evidence. For example, in *Esso West Africa Inc. v T. Oyegbola*,⁷⁴ the Supreme Court stated "the law cannot be and is not ignorant of modern business methods and must not shut its eyes to the mysteries of the computer." Also, in the case of *Federal Republic of Nigeria v Femi Fani-Kayode*,⁷⁵ the respondent was charged with the offence of money laundering and statement of account belonging to the respondent was to be tendered in evidence. Relying on section 97 of the old Evidence Act, the respondent objected to tendering this statement of account. The trial court upheld the objection and rejected the statement of account. However, the Court of Appeal held that, the term "banker's Books" includes all books of every kind used in ordinary course of business in the bank and could also include other methods and devices used to keep records in the bank. Recently, in *F.R.N v. Fani-Kayode*, the Court of Appeal, following the earlier Supreme Court decisions in *Yesufu v ACB and Anyaebosi v R T Briscoe*⁷⁶ held that the computer printout of a bank statement was admissible under section 97 (1) and (2) of the old Evidence Act.

Electronic evidence, also known as digital evidence is information stowed in electronic form and sought to be tendered in evidence; and includes, digital photos, phone records and call logs, emails, instant messaging, spread sheets, DVDs and CDs, social media records-twitter, Facebook, Myspace, chatrooms etc. When tendered in evidence, the questions that usually determine the admissibility of digital evidence relates to (a) method of generating the evidence-whether it was properly obtained, (b) its relevance under section 1 of Evidence Act, whether it is original or a copy,(d)is it direct evidence or hearsay,(e) weight of the evidence under section 34 of Evidence Act; and (f) its reliability certificate. In terms of admissibility of electronically generated documents such as emails, text messages, information from social media, etc., section 84 of EA 2011 lays down conditions under which such pieces of evidence can be admissible.⁷⁷ For example, electronic signature is admissible if it can be shown that a stipulated procedure was followed by the person executing a symbol or followed some other security procedure for the purpose of verifying that an electronic signature was made to an electronic record under section 93 (1) (2) (3) of the Evidence Act 2011

Although electronic evidence is admissible to prove cybercrimes the question is how easy can digital evidence be generated? Obtaining digital evidence for purposes of prosecuting cybercrime is never as easy and or straightforward as it seems even though computers have made the process easier through

⁷¹ Sections 77,76,78,90-98,100,101 of the Evidence

⁷² 76 F. Supp. 2d. 733 775 (S.D. Tex 1999)

⁷³ 208 F. 3d 633 (7th Cir.2000).

⁷⁴ (1969) 1NMLR 194.

⁷⁵ CA/2009

⁷⁶ (2010) 14 NWLR Part 1214 p.481, see particularly the opinion of Salauwa JCA at page 506-507.

⁷⁷ The conditions that must be fulfilled in under the section are: a certificate produced by party seeking to tender computer generated document; identifying the document and describing how it was produced; giving particulars of the computer used; regular use of computer during relevant period to process & store information; similar information was stored and produced; operating properly; ordinary course of activities- (information which was supplied to the computer);and signed by person occupying responsible position in relation to the computer or relevant activities.

the ability to conduct searches of hard drives remotely via the Internet. Some of the main difficulties, however, relate to obtaining permission to conduct such a search, securing the relevant access to the device (s) such as a password, decrypting data that have been encrypted, and imaging a hard drive without interfering with the evidence. There is also the practical problem of conducting searches quickly so that data is not unlawfully removed.

Locating and Securing Relevant Material

Locating and securing digital evidence often pose formidable challenge in the investigation and prosecution of cybercrimes as the act of switching on a computer can potentially alter critical evidence.⁷⁸ This makes it necessary for investigators to search through vast quantities of data in order to locate the information they seek. A major problem concerns the seizure of digital evidence from hard drives on networked computers in which both relevant and irrelevant material (as well as legally privileged material) are stored. The practical problem arises when imaging hard drives and then having to determine which material is relevant to the charges in question.

This creates problems with search warrants where non-specified data are included in the hard drive, arguably leading to the invalidity of the whole search and seizure procedure. It is practically impossible to examine 80GB of data held on a hard drive in order to determine what is relevant. In the United Kingdom for example, the problem of un-separated material seized on hard drives was resolved when legislative amendments to the Criminal Justice and Police Act 2001 came into force.⁷⁹ Other problems relate to disabling networks when seizing data, especially for large public or private sector organizations which rely on 24 hour access to networks, and also the problem of offenders storing data externally on other people's computers in order to evade detection.

Search and Seizure

Two methods of obtaining data from a computer system can be distinguished on technical and legal criteria. In the first, data is obtained as part of a search of premises or the place where the system is located. Section 45 of the Nigeria CPPA, empowers law enforcers to arrest, search and seize property -computers and other electronic devices associated with cybercrime. The second involves the interception or monitoring of data being transmitted from, to or within the system, such as provided in Nigeria under section 39 of the 2015 CPPA. This is an important distinction as remote access to computers via the Internet can sometimes result in the search amounting to an interception of telecommunications that needs to comply with special rules concerning warrants. One recent case involved the investigation of two Russian computer hackers, Vasily Gorshkov and Alexey Ivanov who stole large numbers of credit card details and attempted to extort money from account holders. In an undercover operation, FBI agents posed as representatives of a security firm and made contact with the accused, ostensibly to discuss employment prospects in the United States.⁸⁰ The two accused demonstrated their hacking expertise for the agents who then invited them to come to the United States. While in the United States the FBI agents used a key-logging program to discover the accused persons' passwords that would provide access to their computers in Russia. They were then arrested and charged with various offences. In order to preserve the computer evidence in Russia, the FBI agents immediately copied data from the servers in Russia via the Internet prior to obtaining a search warrant in the United States. The defence raised various objections to this arguing that the search was unconstitutional, being in breach of the Fourth Amendment that requires warrants to be issued prior to searches being conducted. The United States court held that the Fourth Amendment did not apply to these actions as the data had been obtained outside the United States. The court also held that there had been no seizure of the data as it had merely been copied but not read prior to the warrant being obtained.⁸¹

Challenges in Detecting Cybercrime

Generally, some challenges surrounding the prosecution of cybercrimes also hold true for detection of cybercrimes such as anonymity and jurisdiction, amongst others. Detection of cybercrimes is particularly more challenging in some criminal activities than in others. For example, detecting crimes against children by pedophiles is difficult because of the veil provided by online activities that enables criminals to interact illegally with children as if they are also children. For pedophiles with some level

⁷⁸ This also includes time and date records

⁷⁹ The Criminal Justice and Police Act, 2001 was introduced to inter alia, amend the Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984, the Police and Criminal Evidence (Northern Ireland) Order 1989 and the Terrorism Act 2000. Amendment of the Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984 is significant as it allows police in England, Wales and Northern Ireland to indefinitely retain DNA samples and fingerprints if they "were taken from a person in connection with the investigation of an offence" irrespective of whether or not the person is charged or found not guilty. 'Offences' under the Act includes cybercrimes. See Criminal Justice and Police Act, available at, <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2001/16/contents>, accessed 18 June 2022.

⁸⁰ More information may can be obtained from <http://www.interpol.int>, accessed 30 August 2022.

⁸¹ See *United States v Gorshkov* 2001 WL 1024026, No. CR-550C (W.D. Wash 23 May 2001).

of technological expertise, they can scramble photos to make them look like teenagers, specifically to be in line with the age they are claiming. This is to lure children they target to think they are mates in order to relate freely with them so as to make it possible for them to exploit the children sexually for various purposes such as sexual exploitation, murder,⁸² etc. For example, in October 2007, Neil, a British Colombian pedophile was identified from photos found on the Internet after "computer experts unscrambled the swirls of colour that had been encoded into the digital photo files to disguise his face." Neil, 32, was arrested soon afterward in Thailand and went on trial in June of 2008 on charges of child sexual abuse.⁸³ He was convicted of the crime of sexual exploitation of children using the Internet and sentenced to imprisonment for five and half years.⁸⁴ The question therefore relates to how cybercrime against children can be detected with ease.

One of the easiest ways is for children themselves to be used as effective tools in uncovering cybercrime targeted at children. This can be done by (a) arming children with valuable knowledge about the operations of cyber underworld, (b) advocacy; and (c) access to media literacy guidelines⁸⁵ by governments, community leaders as well as parents and organizations.

Securing the International and National Cyberspace against Cybercrime

The Interpol,⁸⁶ the UN and the International Telecommunication Union (ITU),⁸⁷ have identified certain characteristics associated with cybercrime: (a) it is a fast growing threat, (b) cybercrime does not have a universal definition, (c) cybercrime comprises crimes that are not new-theft, fraud, etc. but are developing and becoming widespread and more damaging due to new opportunities offered by the internet, (d) unlike in the past where cybercriminals were mainly individuals and small groups, sophisticated criminal networks now engage in cyber criminality; and (e) it transcends borders. Having identified these characteristics of cybercrime, in addition to the volume of risks associated with the availability of huge number of ICT facilities, particularly computers, which has triggered serious problems for individuals and groups; and pose risks to national security and safety, countries are eager to secure their cyberspace through collective and or individual efforts.⁸⁸

In Nigeria for example, a National Cyber Strategy and Policy was adopted in 2014 to highlight the need to secure the national cyberspace and to stipulate strategy by which law enforcement agencies would do that.⁸⁹ The National Cyber Strategy⁹⁰ now complements the Cybercrime Act law enforcement efforts.

At the international level, European countries for purposes of securing international cyberspace adopted the Budapest Convention. Presently, the international community is advocating for and making efforts towards the adoption of another cybercrime treaty to develop strategies that build upon the EU Cybercrime Convention to secure the international cyberspace against cybercrimes. In that respect, the United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) held a Special Event on "Cyber security and Development", organized jointly by the Department of Economic and Social Affairs (DESA) and the International Telecommunication Union (ITUJ) on 9 December in New York to discuss ways to (1) build awareness at the international policy level by providing ECOSOC Members with a picture of the current situation and challenges concerning cyber security and its links to development; (2) identify a range of best practice policies and initiatives in place around the world to build a culture of cyber security; and (3) explore options for a global response to rising cybercrime.⁹¹

⁸² For example, in United Kingdom (UK) a 14-year-old boy who loved gaming was groomed by pedophile and murdered in 2014. See <http://www.theguardian.com>, accessed 30 July 2016

⁸³ More information regarding this can be found at, <http://www.cbc.ca/news/world/interpol-releases-images-of-suspected-pedophile-1.754506>, accessed 30 June 2022

⁸⁴ Ibid

⁸⁵ Note that the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has issued media literacy guidelines to everyone who uses online platform for whatever reason. See ITU, Digital Literacy and Citizenship in the 21st Century; available at <http://www...> see also ITU, The ITU National Cybersecurity Strategy Guide (2011), pp. 25-31; available at, <http://www.itu.int>; accessed 22 August 2022.

⁸⁶ More information about the establishment, structure, functions and powers as well as its mission can be found at <http://www.interpol.int>; accessed 22 august 2016.

⁸⁷ ITU is the United Nation's specialized agency for information and communication technologies-ICTs. It is an organization based on public-private partnership (PPP) with membership of 193 countries and almost 800 private-sector entities and academic institutions. Headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland, the organization has 12 regional and area offices around the world. More information about the organization can be found at' <http://www.itu.int>; accessed 22 June 2022

⁸⁸ This is also in recognition of the fact that there is a shift in criminal landscaping, with particular reference to the modus operandi, with digital facilities opening a new vista for new digital crimes. Consequently, trillions of dollars have been lost to computer crimes by individuals, groups, organizations, and governments, amongst others.

⁸⁹ See generally the National Cyber Strategy and Policy, 2014.

⁹⁰ Note that the National Cyber Strategy and Policy was signed by the National Security Adviser in 2014, which means it became operational before the Cybercrime was passed in 2015

⁹¹ More information can be obtained at <http://www.itu.net>, accessed 30 August 2016

The desire by the international community to adopt international strategy for combating cybercrimes is aroused by identification of the highlighted threats that cybercrimes pose to national security and national development.

CONCLUSION

Habitually law enforcement like to distinguish between two main types of cybercrime, i.e. advanced cybercrime⁹² and cyber-enabled crime, for ease of enforcement.⁹³ In both types however, the threat cannot be quantified and this fact is agreeable to the international community. This is notwithstanding that the cyberspace provides good opportunity for the world to interact. In the aftermath of the 2016 Rio Olympics for instance, the ITU observed:

"Billions of people around the world experienced the Olympic Games like never before, thanks in part to information and communication technologies (ICTs)."

This statement represents one of the many advantages of expansion in the ICT industry. As much as ICT attracts the good, it also attracts the bad and the ugly.

The point has already been made that the potential impact of cyber attacks and disruptions is increasing due to continuing digitization of existing business models and adversary groups' desire to disrupt information flows.

Generally, detecting and prosecuting cybercrimes is fraught with serious challenges and therefore require cooperation between countries, especially whenever the need arises to extradite or receive information that would aid the prosecuting country. Cooperation in this respect is still lacking, especially between "developed and developing countries,"⁹⁴ a situation that the UN fears, could result in "safe havens" "where cybercriminals can make use of the legal loopholes, and the lack of strong security measures present sometimes in developing countries to perpetrate cybercrimes"⁹⁵ While the challenges are global, they are particularly more daunting for developing countries that do not have sufficient capacity to combat cyber-attacks and cybercrime, and its global threat to cyber safety. This explains, to a considerable measure, paucity of successful prosecutions in Nigeria in the area of cybercrime even though there are constant reports of cyber criminality.⁹⁶

Undoubtedly the challenges surrounding the detection and prosecution of cybercrimes are enormous, including lack of technology sustainability,⁹⁷ particularly in developing countries. But online users can help stem the tide of cyber criminality and consequently reduce challenges to investigators and prosecutors by first learning how to protect themselves in the following ways: (a) guarding their identities and information when they go online, (b) ensuring that public computers are not used for transactions that require online payment, (c) not responding to phony emails and offers that ask for password and or personal information; and (d) ensuring that their computers are protected with strong, updated security software.

⁹² This type of cybercrime is sometimes referred to as high-tech crime. It includes sophisticated attacks against computer hardware and software.

⁹³ Cyber-enabled crime constitutes many 'traditional' crimes which have taken a new turn with the advent of the internet, such as financial crimes, terrorism, offences against children and many others

⁹⁴ UNODC, *Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime* (2013: New York, United Nations), pp. 225-233.

⁹⁵ UNODC, *Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime* (2013: New York, United Nations), pp. 55-60.

⁹⁶ Adeyemi Adepun, "25% of cybercrime cases unresolved", *Guardian Newspaper*, 1 September 2015, available at <http://www.t.guardian.ng>; accessed 22 August 2022

⁹⁷ A. Nuredini, *Challenges in combating cybercrime* (2014) *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* vol. 5, No. 19, 592